

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**A Case Report****INTRA OSSEOUS HEMANGIOMAS (IOH) OF THE PROXIMAL
FEMUR: A CASE REPORT****Mohammed Saleh Aldamegh¹, Mohammed Abdulrahman Alolayan²,
Nawaf Faisal Almukaibil³**¹MBBS, Qassim University, Unaizah College of Medicine, Unaizah, Saudi Arabia.^{2,3}MBBS, Imam Muhammed Ibn Saud Islamic University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.**Greetings:***We are submitting a manuscript entitled for possible publication on your journal .**We confirm that this work is original and has not been published elsewhere.**I declare that all authors have read and approved this submission and I have given appropriate credit to everyone who participated in this work.**This manuscript will not be submitted for publication elsewhere until a decision is made regarding its acceptability for publication in Journal of (Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences).**This journal is the ideal place to present this manuscript. It is unique journal, which will be an honor to the study.***Corresponding author:****Mohammed Saleh Aldamegh,***MBBS, Qassim University, Unaizah College of Medicine,
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*Please cite this article in press Mohammed Saleh Aldamegh et al **Intraosseous Hemangiomas (IOH) Of The Proximal Femur: A Case Report.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).*

INTRODUCTION:

Intraosseous hemangiomas are considered one of the rare benign vascular primary bone tumors that account for 1 % [1]. The incidence of this kind of tumor happens more common in female in comparing to male [2]. Almost all the cases of (IOH) originate from vertebra or skull by 75 % while remaining of 25 % came from scapula, ribs clavicle and pelvic [3-5].

Case Report:

20 years old male presented with pain in the right femur that was preventing him from walking and it was progressive over time.

On X-ray (Fig.1), there is a lytic lesion with cortical disruption and pathological fracture at the proximal right femur. Further CT scan (Fig.1) was requested and it was not informative

MRI (Fig. 2) showing bone lesion involving the intertrochanteric region and the lesser trochanter of the right femur associated with soft tissue edema.

Fig. 1:

The X-ray and CT show an ill-defined predominantly lytic lesion with wide zone of transition demonstrated at the proximal femur with cortical disruption/pathological fracture at the lesser trochanter.

Fig. 2:

MRI demonstrate lobulated eccentric bone lesion involving the intertrochanteric region and the lesser trochanter of the right femur extending inferiorly along the medial femoral cortex. There is associated surrounding soft tissue edema.

DISCUSSION:

Intra-osseous hemangioma are considered one of the rare benign vascular primary bone tumors that account for 1 % [1].

Our literature revealed a barely articles declamation about Intraosseous hemangiomas in appendicular skeletons.

Regarding radiological view of our case by X-RAY and CT scan (Fig. 1), that shows an ill-defined predominantly lytic lesion with wide zone of transition demonstrated at the proximal femur with

cortical disruption/pathological fracture at the lesser trochanter.

On MRI (Fig. 2), Lobulated, eccentric bone lesion involving the intertrochanteric region and the lesser trochanter of the right femur extending inferiorly along the medial femoral cortex. There is associated surrounding soft tissue edema.

Our patient was treated with surgical removal of the tumor and internal fixation by dynamic hip screws (Fig. 3).

Intraosseous hemangiomas are asymptomatic in the majority of the cases while in the peripheral and pelvic bones are symptomatic [2,6,7].

The patient that we report about him presented with pain in the right femur that was preventing him from walking and it was progressive over time.

In other case of 22 years old female came with pelvic mass and tenderness for 1 month without evidence of trauma

In a case of 25 years old women that complains of left hip pain which preventing her from walking while our case shows male complain of right side femur pain [8].

Fig. 3:

[9].

Post treatment x-ray after tumour removal and fixation with dynamic hip screws.

CONCLUSION:

Intraosseous hemangiomas of the appendicular skeletons are one of the rare cases have been seen in medical field [1, 3-5], thus those kind of the case reports show the sign, symptoms, investigations that include radiological and histopathological features and then finally the management that will give valuable information to those who interested as well as who may facing same as these cases in the future.

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